

RESPONSIBILITIES OF A STUDENT INTERN IN ORGANIZING CONTINUOUS TEACHING PRACTICE

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Annotation: This time is spent on studying educational, reference and methodological literature in libraries, on visiting and analyzing lessons and extra-curricular activities, on organizing and conducting parenting meeting, participation in collective and individual forms of methodological work, attending inspection at the university, maintaining accounting and reporting documentation, for preparing and writing a report on continuous teaching practice.

Key words: methodological literature, inspection, teaching practice, meeting, organizing.

During continuous teaching practice, by order of the school director, the student trainee must be assigned to a specific class. The student trainee has the opportunity to learn, analyze, synthesize the work process (of the class teacher and the subject teacher), ongoing educational and training activities; psychological and pedagogical work.

The working time of each working day of an intern student must be at least 5-6 hours (based on 4+2). This time is spent on studying educational, reference and methodological literature in libraries, on visiting and analyzing lessons and extra-curricular activities, on organizing and conducting parenting meeting, participation in collective and individual forms of methodological work, attending inspection at the university, maintaining accounting and reporting documentation, for preparing and writing a report on continuous teaching practice. [9, стр.14-15]. During the period of continuous teaching practice, the student intern is obliged to:

- taking into account the analysis and synthesis of the student intern's work schedule and internal rules in which he undergoes continuous teaching practice, along with other student interns, comply with all generally accepted conditions and requirements of the administration; be careful, tactful, polite, organized, disciplined, do not allow lateness or absences from classes without a good reason (you should come to practice 15-20 minutes before the start of classes);

- support and assistance in fulfilling all responsibilities assigned to the class teacher and subject teacher in terms of organizing classes or lessons, class hours and educational activities;

- organization and development of all types of work provided for by the program and individual practice plan, mandatory presence at meetings, the ability to conduct them correctly (how to write minutes correctly), the ability to conduct them pedagogical council, pedagogical councils, meetings methodologist, etc.;

- correctly keeping a diary (recording of a student intern's daily visit to a general education institution) in practice according to the established form, where the student intern records the activities of his day in continuous teaching practice, assessed by practice managers (using a five-point system);

- an integrated approach to undergoing continuous teaching practice in order to conduct effective career guidance work among students, aimed at familiarizing them with the features

of admitting students to universities for the next academic year and training them at this pedagogical faculty;

-promoting and introducing modern and advanced pedagogical views and ideas on organizing the learning process among the teaching staff, conducting effective educational and research work;

-conducting a planned record of all ongoing activities, according to an individual plan for continuous teaching practice and collecting all the necessary information for writing a report on the practice;

-submission of all necessary documents for continuous teaching practice [9].

Main tasks and responsibilities of the class teacher:

-familiarizing the student trainee with the class staff, with the content and planning of educational work in the group, the contingent of students in the supervised class, informing about academic performance and psychological what characteristics of individual students;

-introducing student trainees into the conditions of the educational and educational process and explaining to them their characteristics;

-introduces changes and the ability to determine (together with the head of practice from the university) the themes and goals of lessons and educational activities (school and extracurricular; classroom and extracurricular activities). The student trainee must prepare and conduct these lessons independently;

-the student trainee must prepare and conduct demonstration lessons, information hours and educational events. Preliminary planning and familiarization with certain educational and educational lessons (sessions) of which intern students are present, familiarizes them with educational planning documentation for these lessons, modern educational publications, information tion-analytical materials and material and technical support;

-content of questions on the organization and methodology of conducting extracurricular lessons (club activities);

-learning the correct design and conduct of lessons (educational process) and educational activities (classroom, extracurricular, school, extracurricular) in assigned groups, participates in their discussion and detailed analysis;

- systematically keeps records of all activities carried out by the student during practice, with current marks (on a five-point scale) in his diary for each working day en;

- gives a comprehensive objective description of the student practitioner based on the results of the entire practice with the setting of a recommended mark (on a five-point scale);

-makes constructive proposals to improve the organization of practice.

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